

**METHODS OF RECREATING PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS
CONTAINING THE COMPONENT "MOUTH"/"OG'IZ" IN ENGLISH
AND UZBEK IN TRANSLATION**

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Annotation

This article explores the methods of translating English and Uzbek phraseological units containing the component "mouth"/"og'iz." It highlights the significance of considering cultural, historical, and linguistic aspects to ensure accurate and idiomatic translation. The study emphasizes that literal translation of such idioms may lead to misinterpretation or loss of meaning, and therefore, equivalence in message rather than form is crucial. Based on a comparative analysis, the phraseological units were categorized into three groups by their degree of adequacy: fully adequate (22%), partially adequate (30%), and inadequate (48%). The research demonstrates that partially and inadequately matched idioms can be translated effectively by finding analogs or through contextual adaptation. Furthermore, the paper underlines the vital role of the translator, whose deep knowledge of the source and target cultures, language systems, and stylistic usage is necessary for successful translation. The findings contribute to the development of linguoculturological approaches and enrich the understanding of interlingual equivalence in phraseological translation.

Key words: phraseological units, idioms, mouth/og'iz component, translation adequacy, linguoculturology, comparative analysis, equivalence, idiomatic translation, cultural aspects, translator competence.

Among the many complex issues studied in modern linguistics, the linguistic aspects of interlingual speech activity known as "translation" or "translation activity" hold an important place. It is well known that although translation and written translation practices have a long history, the field of translation studies is one of the younger branches of linguistics. Incidentally, at the beginning of the 20th century, particularly after World War I, there was a growing focus on learning new languages worldwide. However, scientific research in this area only began to emerge in the 1950s. Over the past half-century, many translations have been carried out, and the general and specific

aspects of translation studies have been explored, analyzed, and hundreds of dissertations have been written based on materials from various languages. A distinctive feature of this period is that the majority of the scientific work conducted focused on issues related to the translation of literary works.

Translation is undoubtedly one of the oldest forms of human activity. As soon as groups of people with different languages appeared in the history of humanity, bilingual individuals who helped facilitate communication between these "multilingual" groups emerged. With the advent of writing, written translators who translated various official, religious, and business texts were added to the ranks of these translators, known as "interpreters." From the very beginning, translation performed an important social function, enabling people and nations to communicate in different languages. The spread of written translations allowed people to widely benefit from the cultural achievements of other nations, disseminate them, and foster mutual influence and enrichment between literatures and cultures. Knowledge of foreign languages allows us to read books in their original versions, but not everyone manages to learn a foreign language, and no one can read books in all or at least the majority of literary languages. The magnificent works of Homer and Shakespeare, Dante and Goethe, Tolstoy and Dostoevsky have been made accessible to all of humanity only through translation. When translating phraseological units, it is essential to pay attention to their cultural, historical, and linguistic aspects in order to convey their meaning accurately. Here are some key points that we believe should be considered during the translation process: Phraseological units are often idiomatic expressions specific to a particular language. Translating them literally can lead to confusion or the loss of the intended message. Instead, it is important to focus on conveying the core concept, meaning, or moral lesson in an idiomatic manner in the target language.

A comparative study of phraseological units containing the components "mouth"/"og'iz" serves as an important tool in identifying the peculiarities of the mentality of different peoples and their commonalities. Within the framework of contemporary linguocultural studies, this approach has gained particular relevance. Overall, the analysis of phraseologisms with the components "mouth"/"og'iz" contributes to the development of the field of linguoculturology in the linguistic experiences of Uzbek and other peoples, as well as aids in the further expansion of the vocabulary of the language.

№	English examples	Uzbek examples
	Fully adequate translation	

1	toilet/potty mouth/ foul-mouthed	Og'zi bemaza. Og'zi buzuq. Og'zi shaloq. Og'zi beposhna
2	closemouthed	og'zi mahkam
3	open-mouthed	og'zi ochilib qolmoq (hayratda qolmoq)
4	make one's mouth water	og'zining suvini keltirmoq
5	mouth waters	og'zining suvi kelmoq
6	take the bread out of (one's) mouth	og'zidan nonini/oshini olib qo'yimoq
7	melt in (one's)/the mouth	og'izda erimoq (mazali)
8	have (one's) heart in (one's) mouth (yoki one's heart leaped into one's mouth) bring smb.'s heart into his mouth (yoki: make smb.'s heart leap out of his mouth)	yuragi og'ziga tiqilmoq; yuragi og'ziga kelmoq;
9	open one's mouth	og'iz ochmoq (so'zlay boshlamoq); og'iz juftlamoq
10	go/fly from mouth to mouth	og'izdan og'izga ko'chmoq/o'tmoq
11	mouth to feed	og'iz (birovning qaramog'ida bo'lgan odam, xo'randa, nonxo'r)
12	keep your mouth shut	og'zingni yum/yop
13	shoot one's mouth off	og'zidan gullamoq
14	Watch your mouth	og'zingga qarab gapir
15	Baloning og'zi (O'limningog'zi)	Doom's doorstep; Mouth of madness; Pandora's box
Partially adequate translation		
1	a big mouth	og'zi bo'sh
2	light-mouthed	og'zi bilan yuradigan; og'ziga kuchi yetmagan; og'zi bo'sh
3	(straight) from the horse's mouth	o'z og'zidan eshitmoq; ishonchli manbadan;
4	the words pour from smb's mouth.	og'iz ko'pirtirmoq
5	condemn oneself out of	tildan ketmoq; o'zining tili o'zining boshini

	one's own mouth	yemoq
6	make a mouth	og'zini burishtirmoq (yosh bolalar kimningdir ustidan kulmoqchi bo'lganda yoki xazil qilmoqchi bo'lganda)
7	a motor mouth	og'zi gapdan bo'shamaydigan, laqma
8	dragon/jungle mouth	og'zidan badbo'y xid kelib turadigan, og'zi sassiq
9	have a plum in (one's) mouth	katta og'iz, og'zi katta
10	stop smb's mouth	og'zini yopmoq
11	from your mouth to God's ears	og'zingga (qantu) novvat\ og'zingga yog' (yoki moy)
12	og'zi botir\polvon	bold speaker
13	og'zi qulog'ida (yoki qulog'iga yetdi)	grin from ear to ear
14	og'zini poylamoq\og'ziga qaramoq	wait for smb to speak; to wait with bated breath
15	og'ziga urmoq\qoqmoq	shut smb's mouth
16	gapi (yoki so'zi) og'zida qoldi	One's words caught in one's throat
17	bash qo'lni (yoki barmoqni, panjani) og'ziga urmoq	to grab everything with both hands; to have sticky fingers; to bite off more than one can chew; to hog everything
18	og'izga (el, yurt, halq, ko'pchilikning og'ziga) tushmoq	to be on everyone's lips (to become the talk of the town; to be in the spotlight)
Inadequate translation		
1	give it mouth	Balandparvoz\katta gapirmoq
2	foam at the mouth	tepa sochi tikka bo'lmoq
3	be all mouth (and no trousers)	og'izda bor, amalda yo'q
4	run off at the mouth	og'zi tinmaydigan, bo'lar-bo'lmas gapirish; og'ziga kelganini o'tlamoq
5	put your money where your mouth is	Gapiga\tiliga javob bermoq
6	have one's mouth made up for smth	biror narsaga nisbatan qaror qabul qilmoq

7	put one's foot in one's mouth	tilini tishlab qolmoq (og'zidan beixtiyor biror sir chiqib ketganda)
8	take the bit in one's mouth	biror narsa\ishni mustaqil boshlamoq
9	get (pull/take) one's finger out of one's mouth	og'ziga qo'lini solib turmasik
10	give somebody a mouthful	Qattiq koyimoq
11	(leave) a bad taste in someone's mouth	kingadir yomon taassurot qoldirmoq
12	take the words out of sb's mouth	kimdir aytmoqchi bo'lib turgan gapni aytmoq
13	put words in/into sb's mouth	kimdir aytmagan narsani aytgan qilib ko'rsatmoq
14	get butter out of a dog's mouth	o'ta mashaqqatli ish haqida
15	born with a silver spoon in one's mouth	boy oilada tug'ilgan bo'lish, tug'ilganidan boylik va imtiyozlarga ega bo'lish
16	Look as if butter wouldn't melt in sb's mouth	qo'y og'zidan cho'pak olmagan; juda yuvosh (bo'lib ko'rinmoq)
17	live from hand to mouth	bazo'r kun kechirmoq; iqtisodiy jihatdan qiynalib yashamoq
18	be laughing out of the other side of (one's) mouth (laugh on the wrong side of one's mouth or face)	xursandchilik uzoqqa cho'zilmaslik
19	be down in (at) the mouth	Hafa bo'lmoq
20	katta og'iz yoki og'zi katta	Boastful / braggart / show-off
21	og'iz solmoq	to ask smb for marriage
22	og'izga olmoq	eat, drink or say
23	og'ziga qaratmoq	hold court; captivate audience
24	olma pish, og'zimga tush, deb o'tirmoq	to wait for a pie to fall from the sky; to wait for something to fall into one's lap; to expect a free lunch
25	og'zining tanobi qochmoq	to smile from ear to ear; to be over the moon
26	ona suti og'zidan ketmagan	Still wet behind the ears; Not yet out of the nest
27	ona suti og'ziga kelmoq	to sweat blood; to go through hell and back

28	og'zi bilan ish bitiradigan	to talk one's way out of something	
29	og'ziga siqqanicha	as much as smb wants; to give with no limit	
30	og'zi(ga) tegdi	to get a taste of	
Jami: 63	To'liq muvofiq -15 (24%)	Qisman muvofiq - 18 (28%)	Nomuvofiq-30 (48%)

CONCLUSION

In the languages being compared, we classified phraseological units with the "mouth" semantic component into three types based on their adequacy: a) Fully adequate phraseological units (14), b) Partially adequate phraseological units (19), c) Inadequate phraseological units (30). The fully adequate phraseological units account for 22% of the total, the partially adequate phraseological units for 30%, and those with inadequacy in translation for 48%. The latter two degrees of adequacy can be addressed by finding analogs or translating them literally. Achieving a high-quality translation is closely related to the human (translator) factor, requiring not only linguistic knowledge but also a deep understanding of the history, culture, and etymology of the conceptual expression tools related to the research object, as well as their development and functional-stylistic aspects.

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